

Social Media as a Tool for Educational Campaigns: Opportunities, Challenges and Implications for Youths in Sub-Saharan Africa

Oluwalola, Gold Opeyemi-Daniel

*Department of Mass Communication
Precious Cornerstone University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.*

godoluwalola@gmail.com

+2348132332572

The conventional educational system in sub-Saharan Africa has been faced with many challenges particularly those that are related to infrastructure and logistics. This explains why the rapid advancement of technology and social media platforms can indeed make them revolutionary agents in educational delivery in the region. The question then is how can the academia, industry, government and the public use the social media collaboratively to foster education among youths in sub-Saharan Africa where school attendance declines sharply as children grow older? This study is anchored within the Quadruple Helix innovation model and it investigates the role of social media as a transformative tool in educational campaigns targeted at youths in sub-Saharan Africa. The theories operationalized were Uses and Gratifications Theory and Media Richness Theory. Based on the systematic review methodology, and synthesis of different case studies, it was found out that there is vast opportunity for personalization and peer-to-peer collaboration with social media but the challenge with algorithmic gatekeeping is that social media algorithm priorities viral or sensational content over educational posts except they are specially promoted. Key challenges that also face social media for education include its potential for addictiveness, misinformation, digital literacy gaps, technological divide and regulatory limitations. Finally, the study calls for stronger collaboration and synergy of resources among the four components of the helix. It was concluded in this scholarly work that while social media is not a panacea, its collaborative and adaptable nature offers significant potential for educational transformation among youths in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Keywords:
Quadruple helix,
Digital education,
Educational
campaigns,
Youth education,
Sub-Saharan
Africa.

Introduction

In the Sub-Saharan part of Africa, the youthful population is of immense advantage presenting the region with developmental opportunities that comes with having a lot of young minds. As it is across the Sub-Saharan Africa, the youth make up about 60% of the entire population (UNFPA, 2022) but one of the major challenges here is that many of the youths in this region are underserved by

formal education system due to various reasons including failure of government to prioritise education, poverty, conflict, deficit in infrastructure and gender disparity (UNESCO, 2021). In Sub-Saharan Africa that is being examined here, over 20% of children of primary school age (6-11years) are out of school, rising to 33% at lower secondary age (12-14years) and nearly 60%

among upper secondary school age (15-17years) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2023).

Now let us examine the flip side taking the nation Nigeria as a case study. Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) is the independent regulatory authority for the telecommunications industry and recently Aminu Maida the executive vice chairman of NCC announced that as at May, 2025 Nigeria has achieved a teledensity of 79.65% and broadband penetration of 48.81% (Patrick-Okwoli, 2025). The gist here is that the youths are the most active users of social media that is growing in use as a result of this broadband penetration (Porter et al, 2022; The Herald, 2023). When we bring the two scenarios together, it is like saying the more our young minds move from childhood to adolescence, the less likely we will find them in the classroom but the more they move from childhood to adolescence the more likely we will find them on social media. This means our work is cut out to use the social media space effectively.

It is needless to say that with the advent of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and the increasing penetration of internet and mobile technologies, social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), TikTok, and YouTube have emerged as alternative educational channels, reshaping how information is shared and acquired and these channels have to be maximized.

Since the appearance of the Triple Helix model of innovations, various extensions of model to higher dimensions, Quadruple, Quintuple as well as N-tuple helices have been proposed (Ivanova, 2014). Quadruple Helix model as a framework for innovation consist of the academia, industry, government and civil society which was added as an upgrade to the triple helix model. The concept of the Quadruple Helix in this study which comprises of the

academia, industry, government, and civil society, hints at an intentional effort to increase practicable innovation through inclusive stakeholder engagement in the educational sector particularly directed to the youths. Within this framework that is been discussed here, social media acts as a channel or point of collaboration for educational campaign delivery. Particularly for young people in a place where access to mobile phone is increasing and internet is getting more affordable but we may not be able to say the same about access to and affordability of classroom education.

Objectives of the Study

This study sets out to achieve the following objectives:

1. Explore how social media facilitates personalised and collaborative learning in educational campaigns.
2. Assess opportunities and benefits of social media in youth-targeted educational campaigns.
3. Identify challenges associated with the use of social media for educational campaigns in sub-Saharan Africa.
4. Examine policy and technological implications for sustainable educational transformation in the region.

Research Questions

1. What role do social media play in enhancing personalised and collaborative learning among youths in SSA?
2. What are the major opportunities and benefits of social media in youth-targeted educational campaign?
3. What challenges hinder the effectiveness of social media fostering education among youths?
4. What are the implications for policy, pedagogy, and technological innovation?

Theoretical Framework

This study is informed by two key theories which I shall be discussing next.

Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT)

Uses and gratifications theory was propounded by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch in the year (1973). It originates from earlier works like Herzog's study in the year 1944 about radio soap opera audiences and Barelson's research on newspaper readership in the year 1949. UGT posits that individuals actively select media platforms to satisfy specific needs such as information, identity formation, integration, and interaction (Blumler & Katz, 1974). This theory provides the framework for explaining the variable of personalization of media content, particularly the challenges that come with it.

First, the social media is their media of choice ahead of other traditional media like television, radio, newspapers and magazines. On the other hand most youths use the social media for what they desire and that is mostly entertainment (Afrobarometer, 2022). This young demography engage with social media content intentionally and based on their individual interest. Hence if they will be successfully targeted in an educational campaign there has to be a way to go past the social media algorithm that predetermines what they are exposed to base on their interest.

Media Richness Theory

This theory was propounded by Daft and Lengel in the year 1986, and it explains how different communication media vary in their capacity to effectively convey information. This theory is suggestive of the fact that communication media vary in richness which can be described as the ability to convey nuanced information (Daft & Lengel, 1986). So, we have platforms like TikTok and

YouTube which offer high richness due to video and audio capabilities, supporting effective learning in educational campaign formats. This theory provides a framework to understanding the technological and pedagogical opportunities that come with the use of social media.

The social media is a "rich" media as the media channels that allow immediate feedback, multiple cues, personal focus, and the use of natural language – are more suitable for complex tasks are designated as "rich" media. Those that are for straightforward information such as memos and emails are designated as "lean" media. The onus is to match the richness of the medium to the complexity of the message to minimize misunderstanding. While the first theory covers the area of choice making ability of the audience, this second theory intimates at the possible reason for the effectiveness of social media over other traditional media of mass communication. This reason is simple; the youths are likely to learn on social media because of its richness in video, audio and feedback mechanism.

Evolution of Social Media in Education

Social media on one hand refer to the internet-based platforms that enable users to create their own content as well as share and engage with other people's content in real-time. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, TikTok, YouTube, and X have in this 21st century have become tools that cannot be done without particularly for social interaction, public engagement, and institutional communication (Kaplan & Haenlein, [2010](#)). Educational campaigns on the other hand refer to organised efforts aimed at informing or educating a target population about specific issues, with the intent of raising awareness, changing

attitudes, or promoting behavioural change (UNESCO, 2021). These campaigns cut across themes that include literacy, health education, environmental awareness, digital safety, and civic responsibility.

On the global scale, social media is fast transitioning to a strategic tool in knowledge dissemination from just a mere space for entertainment (Manca & Ranieri, 2016). In Africa, initiatives such as #AfricaEducatesHer and UNESCO's YouthMobile is also helping to integrate platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp to reach learners remotely. So, to an extent, educational contents are peddled here and there on the social media but then, how can it be used intentionally to achieve maximum impact on the young ones that are already on the social media platforms. I have to say that we are in a world that is fast evolving technologically and the educational sector cannot afford to be left behind. The youths particularly are naturally open to new things and since they have adequately embraced the new media, let us meet them on their platform.

Youth Engagement with Social Media in SSA

Although, figures and statistics from reputable data gathering organisations on the use of social media among youths in sub-Saharan Africa is limited, it is still obvious that the use is on the increase. According to Statista (2024), over 75% of internet users aged 16–34 in Sub-Saharan Africa are active on at least one social media platform.

Youths in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) represent a large and rapidly expanding cohort of social-media users though with varying sizes from nation to nation. Mobile broadband is also increasing throughout the territory and this is encouraging. Also, falling

handset prices and increasing digital literacy is driving a noticeable growth in the use of internet and social media across the region (GSMA, 2023; ITU, 2023). Across national and regional surveys, WhatsApp, Facebook, Youtube and Instagram emerge as dominant platforms, with TikTok showing the fastest growth among younger cohorts (Pew Research Centre, 2022; GSMA, 2023).

The youthful population makes use of social media for reasons as broad as social connections, economic activity, information seeking, learning and civic participation. Some of the youths also use them for informal peer learning, study groups and micro-tutorials using these media to prepare for examinations (UNICEF, 2023).

Personalised and Collaborative Learning on Social Media

Personalised learning in this context refers to the mode by which educational experiences such as pace, learning approaches and content are tailored in a way that it will match individual students' needs, strengths, interests and motivations (U.S. Department of Education, 2010; Lokey-Vega & Stephens, 2019). The aim of this is to increase engagement, deepen learning, and improve the outcomes of the entire process by aligning tasks with learner profiles. Social media has algorithmic personalization and this makes it possible for learners to receive content tailored to their needs. For example, platforms like YouTube help curate educational content based on user preferences (Ngussa & Mbuti, 2021).

Collaborative learning as a concept is an instructional strategy where students work in small groups to achieve a shared academic goal thereby maximizing their learning and also maximizing the learning of others (Johnson et al., 1990; University of Florida,

2016). WhatsApp groups and Facebook communities are examples of social media platforms that foster peer-to-peer collaboration and knowledge sharing.

Methodology

This study adopts systematic review of literature- a review of conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature. This study also synthesizes data from case studies right here in Nigeria, from Kenya and also from Ghana. Included among the secondary data are reports from UNESCO, African Union, NGOs, data from academic journals and empirical studies from 2018–2024 including surveys and social media statistics from Statista and Pew Research Center.

Opportunities of Social Media in Educational Campaigns

The chances that social could really serve as a medium for educational transformation in Sub-Saharan Africa is high, owing to some salient factors which shall be examined now.

Overall Increase in Mobile Phone Accessibility

As it is, more young people are having access to mobile phones now, with mobile penetration exceeding 49% in SSA (GSMA, 2024). And since social media provides cost-effective access to educational content, campaigns can reach rural and marginalised youth, bypassing traditional infrastructural constraints. Many of the nations in Sub-Saharan Africa do not have adequate infrastructure to support the education of the young ones even with the current effort of the private sector (UNESCO, 2021). Using social media as an opportunistic platform to train up the young ones is like meeting them where they are.

Presence of personalised Learning Algorithms and Data Analytics

The AI algorithm that is present on social media allow them to make content available to targeted users based on their history, interests and their interactions on the platforms. This enhances self-paced learning, especially for vocational training and exam preparations which is when students become most interested in educational contents. Additionally, social media platforms are able to offer analytics that will help in monitoring and evaluating these campaigns performance in real-time. It is easier to target those that will be in need of the educational content the most and also easily measure those who use the content made available.

Cost-effectiveness

Compared to traditional media, social media campaigns are significantly cheaper, yet, they are able to offer broader reach (Effing et al., 2011). Recently though, the cost of data is on the rise particularly in a nation like Nigeria. Nevertheless it is still cheaper than television- think about buying the television set, subscribing for cable, getting a reliable power source before a young person can access educational content. It is also easier to reach a larger number of people on social media at a lesser cost.

User Engagement and Peer-to-Peer Collaboration

The interactive nature of this new media fosters community building and dialogue, and this in turn increases message retention (Kietzmann et al., 2011). For instance, some of the widely used visual platforms like TikTok and Instagram, enable short, engaging educational clips and campaigns such as “#MathWithTikTok” in Kenya and Nigeria’s “#DigitalSkillsNG” are already

leveraging on these to simplify STEM concepts for youths.

Omoyele and Musa (2022) reiterate that other platforms like WhatsApp and Telegram facilitate the formation of study groups, where learners support one another and collaborate across geographical boundaries. The youths will be able to meet other students in different parts of Africa and in extension, the world.

Challenges of Using Social Media for Educational Campaigns

Cognitive Challenges

Social Media abets Distraction

On most social media platforms, as you are watching video, you may still be scrolling through other videos which reduces the capacity to grasp most of the content of the original video been watched. Infact, some bring other suggestions before you are done watching one. The intent is to keep you on their platform to watch as many videos and advertisements as possible. In a study by Siebers et al. (2022), a three week experience sampling study of 300 adolescents (nearly 22,000 assessments) was conducted, and it was found out that 77% experienced distraction related to social media, regardless of individual FoMO (Fear of Missing Out), self-control strategies, or parental restrictions. Also, according to Gaillard et al. (2025) after only three minutes of social media scrolling, young adults showed decreased prefrontal cortex activation and felt less focused, this is in contrast to increased brain activity seen during mobile gaming or TV viewing. If social media abets distraction, distraction abets reduced productivity. Moreover, Flanigan and Babchuk (2019) also found out that frequent daily usage of Facebook and the internet for leisure correlates with higher distraction and lower GPA among college students.

Similarly, Chiossi et al. (2023) found out in an experimental study, that TikTok short video consumption significantly impaired performance on intention based memory tasks compared to Twitter, Youtube, or media use (Chiossi et al. 2023). Except one actively choses what he or she uses social media for, it can be very disruptive. This is the more reason the narrative on social media platform should be changed from core entertainment to education and wellbeing of the mind, such that if distraction will occur, it will be to something beneficial to the mind.

Addictiveness

Another sad thing is that social media apart from reducing the ability to focus can be very addictive. In a study that tracked over 4,000 young participants in a period of over four years, it was found that 41% of the participants exhibited high or increasing addictive social media use. These behaviours were associated with 2-3 times higher risk of suicidal thoughts and behaviours independent of total screen time (The Guardian, 2025). A digital trace-based TikTok study showed that highly likely addicted users spent more time using the app and returned frequently throughout the day, though behavioural prediction models showed modest accuracy (Yang et al., 2025). Another web based survey of 505 WeChat users highlighted that emotional and functional attachment to the platform predicted addictive behaviour and this was driven by enjoyment, social interaction, informational support, system quality and personalization (Emerald Study, 2020).

Algorithmic Gatekeeping

Evidently, social media algorithms prioritise viral or sensational content, sometimes at the expense of educational posts. This is not to deny the fact that more often than not, young people also seem to

engage sensational content than educational ones. This limits the organic visibility of educational campaigns unless boosted through paid promotion. This may eventually lead to wasted effort as the medium is more organically suitable for entertainment and vibes. This should not be seen as totally negative but should put more responsibility on stakeholders to shoulder the cost and fill the social media platforms with materials that engages the mind and makes the mind more productive.

Technological challenges Digital Divide

Despite increasing internet penetration, disparities exist between the wealthy and those that don't have enough. In rural areas of countries like Ethiopia or Niger, connectivity remains below 20%, which limits how far these campaigns can go (ITU, 2023). Moreover, access to devices, internet connectivity, and digital literacy remains a major challenge in these rural and low-income areas, excluding a part of the populace from benefitting from educational campaigns.

Data Costs and Device Limitations

Youth from low income families and nations face financial barriers to consistent access due to high data costs and lack of smartphones capable of supporting media contents that are only accessible through the internet (Alliance for Affordable Internet, 2023). This is unfortunate as it means many from low income earning families will miss out of educational campaigns on social media and eventually, multiplicity of channels will be inescapable. So, as we engage the youths on social media, we should not stop engaging them on television and particularly on radio to reach those in rural places.

Challenges with the Medium Misinformation and Content Credibility

Social media can be likened to a two edged sword that has both advantages and

disadvantages for the users. The same openness that we find on social media that allows campaign spread so easily also enables the dissemination of false or misleading educational contents. Without adequate regulation of the social media platform, there may be a spread of myths, especially on health or civic education. This rapid dissemination of false educational information such as fake school reopening dates or misleading health education can undermine the credibility and objectives of genuine campaigns. If the social media will be used for such campaigns as this, we cannot but call for a level justifiable regulation of the platform.

Content Fatigue and Engagement Gaps

If and when there is content overload, audiences may scroll past educational posts except those posts are extremely engaging and also resonate with their emotions. But it will be difficult to keep coming up with materials that are highly engaging. Nevertheless the content that will keep the youths engaged have to be really appealing and impactful.

Case Studies

Nigeria: Digital Literacy for All Initiative

The Nigerian government launched a campaign in partnership with Facebook and Google in 2024 targeting 10 million youths with digital skills via various social media platforms like YouTube, WhatsApp, and Instagram. The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) under President Tinubu's Renewed Hope Agenda is the agency saddled with the responsibility of launching the Digital Literacy for all (DL4ALL). The goal of the initiative was to raise Nigeria's digital literacy level to 70% by 2027 and ultimately 95% by 2030 (Federal Ministry of

Communications, Innovation & Digital Economy, 2024; Guardian Nigeria, 2024)

DL4ALL's design is that of inclusivity, as its reach spans students in tertiary institutions, the informal sector, and the federal workforce. One of the notable differences in its operationalization is the partnership with the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC). This initiative of the Federal Government of Nigeria deploys 80 Corps members per state to train up to 600 individuals each month, thereby enabling outreach to all 774 local government areas in the nations (ThisDay Live, 2024). This is not particularly targeted at the youths but targeted at all age range.

Kenya: KeepLearning Campaign

Led by the Ministry of Education and Safaricom Foundation, this campaign used Twitter and YouTube for broadcasting national curriculum content during COVID-19 school closures. Keep Kenya Learning (KKL) was launched in 2020 during widespread COVID-19 school closures in Kenya, it is a collaborative initiative developed by EdTech East Africa, Metis Collective and the Regional Education Learning Initiative (RELI). The core aim of this project is to empower parents and caregivers to support their children and wards who learn from home through accessible and inclusive tools and guidance (EdTech East Africa et al., 2020; World Bank, 2022).

The campaign curates and amplifies high-quality digital and non-digital learning materials across multiple channels- social media, Tv, local community-based organisations (CBO) and schools, particularly targeting low-income, rural, and informal settlement communities (HundrED, 2021; RELI, 2021). This is not directed to the youths but used an indirect approach to empower those who have access to them.

Rori: The WhatsApp AI Tutor in Ghana

This is another innovative solution that came out of Ghana. It is an AI-powered mathematics tutor that operates entirely within the WhatsApp messaging platform. It is designed for upper primary to junior secondary students (Grades 3–9) and it provides interactive lessons, problem-solving guidance, and instant feedback to the students thus enabling them to practice mathematics at their own pace in a familiar digital environments (Adotey et al., 2024). Rori uses WhatsApp's conversational interface to simulate a one-on-one tutoring experience. On Rori, learners can send a math problem or select from provided exercises, and Rori will respond with step-by-step explanations, hints, and corrective feedback. The system's AI algorithms are tailored to local curricula and learning objectives, ensuring that the content aligns with Ghana Education Service standards (Adotey et al., 2024). Also noteworthy is that the platform requires only a basic smartphone and minimal internet bandwidth, addressing significant barriers to EdTech adoption in low-resource settings (World Bank, 2023).

To empirically test the effectiveness of the initiative, in a randomised controlled trial involving approximately 1,000 students from 11 schools in Ghana, Rori users demonstrated significant improvements in mathematics performance compared to the control group. This invention was recorded to yield an effect size of 0.37 standard deviations with a p-value < 0.001, indicating a noticeable statistical significance (Adotey et al., 2024). The study also reported higher engagement rates among students using Rori, particularly in rural and peri-urban areas where access to traditional tutoring services is limited.

These three case studies show the three ways the youths can be targeted for

educational purposes. They can be targeted together with the adults, they can be targeted through the adults and they can be targeted directly. The Rori situation explains how they can be targeted directly. Obviously for

optimal results, those within the primary school age should be reached through their parents and caregivers while those who are older should be reached directly.

Implications and Recommendations for all sectors

Figure 6. The two way implications of the helix's synergy on youth education and youth education on the helix.

In the diagram above, the helixes working together to foster youth education will eventually benefit from the process. The youths that are been catered for today, will eventually populate the civil society; take over the academia, the industry and the government.

Academia

Educators must adapt content for mobile-first delivery, incorporating visuals and interactivity. Training is needed on content creation for platforms like TikTok, YouTube, and Facebook Live.

Digital media literacy should be integrated as a subject or course into the syllabus of secondary and tertiary institutions. Critical thinking must also be prioritised in curricula to ensure youth can navigate the digital information ecosystem responsibly even in the face of misinformation, disinformation, hate speech and the likes.

Government

Policies should focus on universal access to digital technology, and regulation that protects against misinformation while ensuring freedom of expression.

Governments and telecommunication providers should endeavor to subsidise the prices of data for educational content to be easily accessible in these Sub-Saharan African nations.

Industry

While designing these campaigns, emphasis must be laid on the consideration of local languages, offline functionality, and

low bandwidth adaptation to ensure inclusivity of all.

Platforms should also strengthen content moderation and fact-checking for educational topics. Platforms should make sure they embed fact-checking partnerships to ensure the reliability of educational content.

Digital Literacy Training should also come from the industry to equip students, teachers, and the public with the skills to critically engage with and create educational content online.

Civil Society

Parents and caregivers should encourage their children and wards to use social media more for educational purposes than for entertainment purposes.

Stakeholders should partner together under the Quadruple Helix model to make educational campaigns realistic at the grass root level. This can be made possible by combining multiple social media channels together with offline campaigns to achieve broader reach and inclusion.

Conclusion

Social media holds immense potential for transforming education in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly for its youthful population. While challenges remain, particularly with consistency in keeping up with the innovative ideas, the Quadruple Helix model offers a collaborative blueprint to harness this potential through personalisation and inclusive innovation. With coordinated efforts from government, academia, industry, and civil society, social media can evolve from a tool of distraction and addiction to one of liberation into educational, economic, and civic empowerment.

References

- Adotey, J., Abudu, I., Bentum, K., Ahedor, E., Owusu-Aning, R., Tisby, E., Boateng, R., Crouch, L., Piper, B., & Angrist, N. (2024). Rori: A conversational AI math tutor on WhatsApp improves learning outcomes in Ghana (arXiv:2402.09809). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.09809>
- Afrobarometer (2022). Youth and digital engagement in Africa
- Afrobarometer. (2020–2023). Round X: Country survey datasets and topline reports.
- Alliance for Affordable Internet. (2023). Affordability report 2023. <https://a4ai.org>
- Berelson, B. (1949). What ‘missing the newspaper’ means. In P. F. Lazarsfeld & F. Stanton (Eds.), *Communications Research, 1948–49* (pp. 111–129). New York: Harper & Brothers.
- Blumler, J. G., & Katz, E. (1974). *The uses of mass communications: Current perspectives on gratifications research*. Sage.
- Chiossi, F., Haliburton, L., Ou, C., Butz, A., & Schmidt, A. (2023). Short-form videos degrade our capacity to retain intentions: Effect of context switching on prospective memory. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.03714>
- CIPESA. (2023). Social media taxation and regulation in Africa.
- Daft, R. L., & Lengel, R. H. (1986). Organizational information requirements, media richness and structural design. *Management Science*, 32(5), 554–571.
- Daft, R. L., & Lengel, R. H. (1986). Organizational information requirements, media richness and structural design. *Management Science*, 32(5), 554–571.

- EdTech East Africa, Metis Collective, & Regional Education Learning Initiative. (2020). Keep Kenya Learning campaign. <https://keepkenyalearning.com/homepage/>
- Federal Ministry of Communications, Innovation & Digital Economy. (2024). Nigeria launches Digital Literacy for All initiative to accelerate economic growth. Abuja: Government of Nigeria. <https://fmcide.gov.ng>
- Flanigan, A. E., & Babchuk, W. A. (2019). The Internet and Facebook usage on academic distraction of college students. *Computers & Education*, 134, 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.02.005>
- Gaillard, A., et al. (2025). Here's what happens to your brain after just 3 minutes of social media. *Scientific Reports*. (Summarised in Herald Sun). <https://www.heraldsun.com.au/health/mental-health/why-social-media-brain-rot-may-be-more-real-than-you-think/news-story/1ac8b9cbb6357da4f8b486bb8a6922e4>
- Emerald Study Authors. (2020). Exploring the mechanism of social media addiction: An empirical study from WeChat users. *Internet Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-08-2019-0347>.
- GSMA Intelligence. (2023). The Mobile Economy: Sub-Saharan Africa 2023. GSMA.
- GSMA. (2024). Mobile economy Sub-Saharan Africa.
- Guardian Nigeria. (2024, July 9). FG launches Digital Literacy for All to accelerate economic growth. <https://guardian.ng/news/fg-launches-digital-literacy-for-all-to-accelerate-economic-growth/>
- Herzog, H. (1944). What do we really know about daytime serial listeners? In P. F. Lazarsfeld & F. Stanton (Eds.), *Radio Research 1942–43* (pp. 3–33). New York: Duell, Sloan & Pearce.
- HundrED. (2021). Keep Kenya Learning – Empowering caregivers to support at-home learning. <https://hundred.org/en/innovations/keep-kenya-learning>
- Inga Ivanova (2014) *Quadruple helix systems and symmetry: A step towards helix innovation system classification*. *Journal of Knowledge Economy*.
- International Telecommunication Union (ITU). (2023). *Measuring digital development: Facts and figures 2023*. ITU.
- ITU. (2023). *Measuring digital development: Facts and figures 2023*.
- Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R. T., & Smith, K. (1990). *Cooperative learning: Increasing college faculty instructional productivity*. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report, 4(1).
- Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1973). Uses and gratifications research. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 37(4), 509–523
- Lokey-Vega, A., & Stephens, J. (2019). A conceptual framework for the personalized learning movement.
- Manca, S., & Ranieri, M. (2016). Facebook and the others. Potentials and obstacles of social media for teaching in higher education. *Computers & Education*, 95, 216–230.
- National Information Technology Development Agency. (2024, September 16). FG to ensure 30 million Nigerians are digitally literate by 2027. Abuja: NITDA. <https://nitda.gov.ng>
- Ngussa, B. M., & Mbuti, I. A. (2021). Use of social media platforms in promoting students' learning in Tanzanian higher

- education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(3), 50–62.
- Omoyele, D. & Musa, H. (2022). WhatsApp and informal learning in Nigerian tertiary education. *African Journal of ICT*, 18(2), 87–101.
- Patrick-Okwoli, L. (2025, July 18). Nigeria's teledensity hits 79.65%, broadband penetration at 48.81%, reports NCC. BusinessDay NG. <https://businessday.ng/technology/article/nigerias-teledensity-hits-79-65-broadband-penetration-at-48-81-reports-ncc/>
- Pew Research Center. (2021–2023). Reports on social media use and internet adoption in developing countries. Pew Research Center.
- Porter, G., Hampshire, K., Milner, J., Munthali, A., Robson, E., de Lannoy, A., Bango, A., Gunguluza, N., Mashiri, M., & Tanle, A. (2022). Mobile phones, gender and female empowerment in sub-Saharan Africa: Studies with African youth. *Technology in Society*, 70, 102020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.102020>
- Regional Education Learning Initiative. (2021). Community-led strategies for home-based learning during school closures. RELI Africa. <https://reliafrica.org>
- Siebers, T., Beyens, I., Pouwels, J. L., & Valkenburg, P. M. (2022). Explaining variation in adolescents' social media-related distraction: The role of social connectivity and disconnectivity factors. *Current Psychology*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03743-5>
- Statista. (2024). Most used social media platforms in Ghana as of Q3 2023. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1176101/leading-social-media-platforms-ghana/>
- Statista. (2024). Number of internet and social media users in Africa.
- The Guardian (2025, June). Teenagers who report addictive use of screens at greater risk of suicidal behaviour, study shows.
- ThisDay Live. (2024, September 16). FG to ensure 30m Nigerians are digitally literate by 2027. <https://www.thisdaylive.com/2024/09/16/fg-to-ensure-30m-nigerians-are-digitally-literate-by-2027/>
- U.S. Department of Education. (2010). Definition of personalized learning.
- UNESCO. (2021). State of education in Africa: 2021 update.
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2023). Education in Africa. Retrieved from <https://uis.unesco.org/en/topic/education-africa>
- UNFPA. (2022). Demographic dividend in Africa.
- UNICEF. (2022/2023). Reports and briefs on adolescents' digital lives and online risks. UNICEF.
- World Bank. (2022). Remote learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in Kenya: Lessons from the Keep Kenya Learning campaign. World Bank Group. <https://documents.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2023). Digital economy for Africa initiative.
- World Bank. (2023). The state of EdTech in Africa 2023. World Bank Group. <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documentsreports/documentdetail/>
- Yang, C., Mousavi, S., Dash, A., Gummadi, K. P., & Weber, I. (2025). Studying behavioral addiction by combining surveys and digital traces: A case study of TikTok.